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Research Paper

Development And Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Estimation of Esmolol HCL from Semisolid Dosage Form

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ABSTRACT

Esmolol Hydrochloride belongs to the class II anti-arrhythmic drugs. Topical Esmolol Hydrochloride used as a Novel Treatment Modality for Diabetic Foot Ulcers. Development and validation of Simple, Precise and Accurate RP-HPLC method for estimation of Esmolol Hydrochloride in Semi solid dosage form. The validation of this method was achieved as per ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines with the optimized experimental conditions. To achieve the proposed method on Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m) column as Stationary Phase and run time was 20 min. The Mobile Phase consists of Acetonitrile:6.8g/L Ammonium acetate buffer (15:85) (pH 5). UV detection was carried out at 221nm. Linearity co-relation co-efficient found is 0.99965. The method was validated by determining its accuracy, linearity and precision. The proposed method is simple, precise, economical and hence can be applied for routine quality control of esmolol hydrochloride in semi solid dosage form.

INTRODUCTION

The chemical name of Esmolol Hydrochloride is methyl 3-(4-{2 -hydroxy-3-[(propan-2-yl) amino] propoxy} phenyl) propanoate hydrochloride.

Esmolol Hydrochloride is the salt form of Esmolol, which belongs to the class II anti-arrhythmic drugs. Esmolol hydrochloride blocks β -1 receptors in cardiac muscle and at higher

doses, it will occlude β -2 receptors and vascular smooth muscle thus directing to its muscle relaxation 2, 3. It has a molecular formula of $C_{16}H_{25}NO_4 \cdot HCl$ with molecular weight 331.8 g/mol. The purpose of this study is to develop a simple, precise, and accurate RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Esmolol Hydrochloride from a semi-solid dosage form and to validate the developed method with study of

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different parameters as per ICH guidelines as No reported RP-HPLC methods for estimation of Esmolol Hydrochloride in Semi solid dosage forms were found.

Esmolol Hydrochloride

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Materials

Drug Substance: Working standards Esmolol Hydrochloride (99.9%), were procured from Mehta API.

Esmolol hydrochloride finished product:

Brand name: Diulcus Gel

Product name: Esmolol HCL 14% w/w

Manufacturer: IPCA Lab Ltd.

Instrumentation:

HPLC instrument with UV-visible detector – Agilent Infinity II

Software: Open lab

Column - Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

UV-visible Spectrophotometer - SHIMADZU 1601 Software - UV probe, version- 2.34

Digital Analytical Balance - OHSUS

Ultra Sonicator -PS 21

Digital pH meter – Lab India

Controlled temperature water bath

Hot air Oven – Kesar

FTIR – SHIMADZU

Melting Point Apparatus – ANALAB Model: ThermoCal50

Chemicals and Reagents: Esmolol Hydrochloride API, Acetonitrile HPLC Grade, Phosphate Buffer, Tetrahydrofuran (THF), Ammonium acetate buffer, Hydrochloric Acid, Methanol HPLC Grade, Sodium Hydroxide pellet, Water: Distill water(Milli-Q), HPLC grade water.

Preparation of Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile:6.8g/L Ammonium acetate buffer (15:85) (pH 5)

Preparation of Standard Solution: Weigh accurately 70 mg of Esmolol hydrochloride WS and transfer into 100 ml volumetric flask. Add water about 60 ml then dissolved it then mark up to 100 ml with water. (Concentration of Esmolol hydrochloride is 700 μ g/ml)

Preparation of Sample solution: Weigh 500 mg (Equivalent to 70 mg) of topical gel and transfer into 100 ml volumetric flask. Add water about 60 ml then dissolved it then mark up to 100 ml with Mobile Phase.

(Concentration of Esmolol hydrochloride is 700 μ g/ml)

Preparation of system suitability solution: Take standard solution for system suitability.

System suitability requirement:

Tailing factor: NMT 2.0 for Esmolol peak

Relative standard deviation: NMT 2.0%

Chromatographic Conditions:

Column: Intsil C₁₈ column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

Flow rate: 1.5ml/min

Total run time (min): 20 min.

Injection volume (μ l) : 20

Column Temperature($^{\circ}$ C): Ambient

Detection Wavelength(nm) : UV 221 nm

IDENTIFICATION CHARACTERIZATION

The identification of taken standard API for experimental work had done for confirmation of its identity, standard quality and purity. The identification had done by taking IR and UV spectra, solubility study and melting point determination.

AND Solubility Study

The solubility of Esmolol Hydrochloride was practically determined by taking 100 mg of the drugs in 100 ml volumetric flasks, adding required quantity of solvent at room temperature and shaken for few minutes. Solubility data for each study was observed and recorded in Table 2.0

Description Terms	Relative Quantities of solvent for 1 parts of
Very Soluble	Less than 1 part
Freely Soluble	From 1 to 10 parts
Soluble	From 10 to 30 parts
Sparingly Soluble	From 30 to 100 parts
Slightly Soluble	From 100 to 1000 parts
Very Slightly Soluble	From 1000 to 10000 parts
Practically Insoluble	More than 10000 parts

Table 1.0 Solubility table as per IP'2014 specification

Solvent	Esmolol Hydrochloride
Water	Soluble
Chloroform	Freely soluble
0.1 N HCl	Soluble
0.1 N NaOH	Soluble
Acetonitrile	Soluble
Methanol	Freely soluble
Ethanol	Freely soluble

Table 2.0 Solubility Data of Esmolol Hydrochloride

Identification by Melting Point Determination

Melting point of Esmolol Hydrochloride has been determined. The melting points of the compounds were taken by open capillary method.

API	Melting point (°C)	
	Reported	Measured
Esmolol Hydrochloride	85.5 °C	85-86 °C

Table 3.0 Melting Point of Drugs

IR Spectra:

The IR Spectra of Esmolol Hydrochloride with its functional group identification, were shown in the

following graph. IR spectra scanning of sample: Esmolol Hydrochloride

Figure 1.0 IR Spectra of Esmolol Hydrochloride

Functional group	Observed value(cm ⁻¹)	Reference value(cm ⁻¹)
C=O	1730	Near 1700
O-H	3224	3400-3200
C-H(Aromatic)	3122	3150-2950
C-H(Aliphatic)	2828	3050-2850
C-H	809	900-690

Table 4.0 IR Spectral interpretation of Esmolol Hydrochloride

METHOD DEVELOPMENT

SELECTION OF WAVELENGTH:

The RP-HPLC Method used UV detection which is depends on proper selection of detection

wavelength. An ideal wavelength is important to get good response for the drugs that can be detected. To determine wavelength for measurement, standard spectra of Esmolol Hydrochloride was scanned between 200- 400nm against diluents. Peak is obtained at 221nm.

Figure 2.0 Overlay UV Spectra of Esmolol Hydrochloride

SELECTION OF COLUMN:

For RP-HPLC method, various columns are available but our main aim is to resolve drug in the presence of excipients. So the C18 column was selected for estimation of Esmolol Hydrochloride. Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

column was chosen to give good peak shape and high resolution, which also provides high peak symmetry, good retention to drug and facilitates the separation of the drug without the interference of excipients within short run time.

Snapshot of Intsil C₁₈ column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m):

SELECTION OF MOBILE PHASE

Mobile Phase: Methanol (MeOH) : 6.8gm/L
Phosphate buffer (5:95) (pH 3)

TRIAL 1:

Detection: 221 nm

Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

Run Time: 32 minutes

Observation: No peak detected.

Figure 3.0 Trial 1: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 2:

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Methanol (MeOH): 6.8gm/L
Phosphate buffer (5:95) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 32 minutes
Observation: No peak detected.

Figure 4.0 Trial 2: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 3:

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Methanol (MeOH): 6.8gm/L
Phosphate buffer (10:90) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 20 minutes
Observation: Two Peak Identified.

Figure 5.0 Trial 3: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 4:

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Tetrahydrofuran (THF) : 6.8gm/L
Phosphate buffer (5:95) (pH 4)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 20 minutes
Observation: No peak detected.

Figure 6.0 Trial 4: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 5

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Tetrahydrofuran (THF) : 6.8gm/L
Phosphate buffer (10:90) (pH 4)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 10 minutes
Observation: Peak Shape not good.

Figure 7.0 Trial 5: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 6

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Tetrahydrofuran (THF) : 6.8gm/L
Phosphate buffer (10:90) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 10 minutes
Observation: Peak not identified.

Figure 8.0 Trial 6: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 7

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L
Ammonium acetate buffer (5:95) (pH 3)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 10 minutes
Observation: No peak detected.

Figure 9.0 Trial 7: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 8

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L
Ammonium acetate buffer(5:95) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 10 minutes
Observation: Peak not identified.

Figure 10.0 Trial 8:

Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 9

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L
Ammonium acetate buffer (6:94) (pH 5)
Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 10 minutes
Observation: Negative peak observed

Figure 11.0 Trial 9: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 10

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L
Ammonium acetate buffer (8:92) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 20 minutes
Observation: Broadening observed.

Figure 12.0 Trial 10: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 11

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L
Ammonium acetate buffer (10:90) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm
Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min
Run Time: 7 minutes
Observation: Tailing observed.

Figure 13.0 Trial 11: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 12-1

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L Ammonium acetate buffer (15:85) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm

Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min

Run Time: 20 minutes

Observation: Peak shape was observed good and sharp. Tailing factor below 1.5.

Figure 14.0 Trial 12-1: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 12-2

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L Ammonium acetate buffer (15:85) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm

Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min

Run Time: 20 minutes

Observation: Peak shape was observed good and sharp. Tailing factor below 1.5.

Figure 15.0 Trial 12-2: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

TRIAL 12-3

Column: Intsil C18 column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μ m)

Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L Ammonium acetate buffer(15:85) (pH 5)

Detection: 221 nm

Flow rate: 1.5 ml/min

Run Time: 20 minutes

Observation: Peak shape was observed good and sharp. Tailing factor below 1.5.

Figure 16.0 Trial 12-3: Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

Optimized Chromatographic conditions :

Chromatographic Parameter	Condition
Column	Intsil C ₁₈ column (300 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile phase	Acetonitrile (ACN) : 6.8 g/L Ammonium acetate buffer (15:85) (pH 5)
Flow Rate	1.5 ml/min.
Total Run Time(min)	20min.
Injection Volume μl	20μl.
Column Temperature(°C)	Ambient.
Detection Wavelength(nm)	UV 221nm

Table 5.0 Optimized Chromatographic conditions

INTRODUCTION OF METHOD VALIDATION PARAMETER

Method validation is the process of documenting or proving that an analytical method provides analytical data acceptable for the intended use. The need to validate a method and the procedure to be followed are matters of professional judgement, although well-prescribed procedures and guidelines are now available that aid in decision making. According to that the various validation parameters to validate each and every above stated method are:

- ✓ Accuracy
- ✓ Precision (Repeatability and Reproducibility)
- ✓ Linearity
- ✓ Range
- ✓ Selectivity/ Specificity

- ✓ Robustness/ Ruggedness
- ✓ Limit of Detection (LOD)/ Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Accuracy

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value. In case of the assay of a drug in a formulated product accuracy may be determined by application of the analytical method to synthetic mixtures of the drug product components to which known quantities of the analyte have been added (i.e. “to spike”).

Accuracy is calculated as the percentage of recovery by the assay of the known added amount of analyte in the sample or as the difference between the mean and the accepted true value, to gather with confidence intervals. Dosage form

assays commonly provide accuracy within 3-5 % of the true value.

The ICH documents recommend that accuracy should be assessed using a minimum of nine determinations over a minimum of three concentration levels, covering the specified range (i.e. three concentrations and three replicated of each concentration).

It may often be expressed as the recovery by the assay of known added amounts

of analyte. Samples are prepared & analyzed and the recoveries of each are calculated.

$\% \text{ Recovery} = (\text{Spiked sample result} - \text{Unspiked sample result}) / \text{Spiked sample result} \times 100\%$

Acceptance criteria:

- The percentage recovery should be within $100 \pm 2.0\%$ for the average of each set of three weights.
- Each individual sample recovery should lie within the range of 98%-102%.
- Coefficient of determination (r^2) should be greater than 0.998.
- There should be no curvature in the residuals plot.

Precision

The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions. Precision may be considered at three levels: repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility. Precision should be investigated using homogeneous, authentic samples. However, if it is not possible to obtain a homogeneous sample it may be investigated using artificially prepared samples or a sample solution. The precision of an analytical procedure is usually expressed as the

variance, standard deviation or coefficient of variation of a series of measurements.

Repeatability

Repeatability expresses the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time. Repeatability is also termed intra-assay precision.

Intermediate precision

The extent to which intermediate precision should be established depends on the circumstances under which the procedure is intended to be used. The applicant should establish the effects of random events on the precision of the analytical procedure. Typical variations to be studied include days, analysts, equipment, etc. It is not considered necessary to study these effects individually. The use of an experimental design (matrix) is encouraged.

$\% \text{ RSD}$ or coefficient of variance (CV) is expressed as,

$$\text{RSD} = \text{CV} = \text{SD}/\bar{X} \times 100$$

$$\text{Standard Error} = \text{SD}/\sqrt{n}$$

Where, n = Number of Replicates taken in the set.

Reproducibility

Reproducibility expresses the precision between laboratories (collaborative studies, usually applied to standardization of methodology). The ICH documents recommends that repeatability should be assessed using a minimum of nine determinations covering the specified range for the procedure (i.e. three concentrations and three replicates of each concentration).

Linearity

A linear relationship should be evaluated across the range (see section 3) of the analytical procedure. It may be demonstrated directly on the

active substance (by dilution of a standard stock solution) and/or on separate weighings of synthetic mixtures of the product components, using the proposed procedure. The latter aspect can be studied during investigation of the range.

Linearity should be evaluated by visual inspection of a plot of signals as a function of analyte concentration or content. If there is a linear relationship, test results should be evaluated by appropriate statistical methods, for example, by calculation of a regression line by the method of least squares. In some cases, to obtain linearity between assays and sample concentrations, the test data may need to be subjected to a mathematical transformation prior to the regression analysis. Data from the regression line itself may be helpful to provide mathematical estimates of the degree of linearity. The correlation coefficient, y-intercept, slope of the regression line and residual sum of squares should be submitted. A plot of the data should be included. In addition, an analysis of the deviation of the actual data points from the regression line may also be helpful for evaluating linearity. Some analytical procedures, such as immunoassays, do not demonstrate linearity after any transformation. In this case, the analytical response should be described by an appropriate function of the concentration (amount) of an analyte in a sample.

For the establishment of linearity, a minimum of 5 concentrations is recommended. Other approaches should be justified.

Acceptance criteria:

- Coefficient of determination (r^2) should be greater than 0.998.
- There should be no curvature in the residuals plot.
- The Y-intercept should not significantly depart from zero.

Range

The range of an analytical method is the interval between the upper and lower levels of analyte (including these levels) that has been demonstrated to be determining with a suitable level of precision, accuracy and linearity using the method as written. The range is expressed in the same units as test results (eg. percent, parts per million) obtained by analytical method.

Acceptance criteria:

- Coefficient of determination (r^2) should be greater than 0.998.
- There should be no curvature in the residuals plot.
- The Y-intercept should not significantly depart from zero.

Specificity

Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically these might include impurities, degradants, matrix etc.

Lack of specificity of an individual analytical procedure may be compensated by other supporting analytical procedure(s). This definition has the following implications:

Identification: To ensure the identity of an analyte.

Purity Tests: To ensure that all the analytical procedures performed allow an accurate statement of the content of impurities of an analyte, i.e. related substances test, heavy metals, residual solvents content etc.

Assay (content or potency): To provide an exact result which allows an accurate statement on content or potency of the analyte in a sample.

Robustness

The robustness of an analytical method is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variation in method parameters and provides an indication of its

reliability during normal usage. The determination of robustness requires that methods characteristic are assessed when one or more operating parameter varied.

Rogudness

The ruggedness of an analytical method is the degree of reproducibility of test results obtained by the analysis of the same samples under a variety of normal test conditions such as different laboratories, different analysts, using operational and environmental conditions that may differ but are still within the specified parameters of the assay.

The testing of ruggedness is normally suggested when the method is to be used in more than one laboratory. Ruggedness is normally expressed as the lack of the influence on the test results of operational and environmental variables of the analytical method.

For the determination of ruggedness, the degree of reproducibility of test result is determined as function of the assay variable. This reproducibility may be compared to the precision of the assay under normal condition to obtain a measure of the ruggedness of the analytical method.

Limit of Detection

The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be detected, but not necessarily quantified, under the stated experimental conditions. It is usually expressed as the concentration of analyte in the sample. The determination of the limit of detection of instrumental procedures is carried out by determining the signal-to-noise ratio by comparing test results from the samples with known concentration of analyte with those of blank samples and establishing the minimum level at which the analyte can be reliably detected. A

signal-to-noise ratio of 2:1 or 3:1 is generally accepted.

The signal-to-noise ratio is determined by dividing the base peak by the standard deviation of all data points below a set threshold. Limit of detection is calculated by taking the concentration of the peak of interest divided by three times the signal-to noise ratio. Other approaches depend on the determination of the slope of the calibration curve and the standard deviation of responses as shown below:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{SD} / \text{Slope of calibration curve}$$

Where, SD = Standard deviation of intercepts of calibration curves.

Limit of Quantification

The limit of quantification (LOQ) is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy. It is usually expressed as the concentration of analyte in the sample. It can be determined by comparing measured signals of samples with known low concentrations of analyte with those of blank samples. The minimum concentration at which the analyte can reliably be quantified is established.

A typical acceptable signal- to- noise ratio is 10:1. Other approaches depend on the determination of the slope of the calibration curve and the standard deviation of responses.

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \text{SD}/\text{Slope of calibration curve}$$

Where, Standard Deviation of intercepts of calibration curves.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Analytical Method Validation

Specificity

The Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride Standard (Figure 18.0) and Esmolol Hydrochloride Blank (Figure 17.0), So the Hydrochloride Sample (Figure 19.0) Show no interference with the Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride Blank (Figure 17.0), So the developed method is Specific.

Figure 17.0 Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride Blank

Figure 18.0 Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride Standard

Figure 19.0 Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride Sample

Linearity and Range

The linearity range for Esmolol Hydrochloride was found to be in the range of 350 to 1050 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Correlation coefficient (r^2) for calibration curve of Esmolol hydrochloride should be found 0.998.

Linearity stock solution: Transfer an accurately weighed quantity of about 140 mg of Esmolol hydrochloride in 100 ml volumetric flask. Add about 60 ml of mobile phase and sonicate to dissolve it. Make volume up to the mark with mobile phase.

50% (350 PPM): Pipette out 2.5 from Stock solution and dilute up to 10 ml with diluent.

80% (560 PPM): Pipette out 4.0 from stock solution and dilute up to 10 ml with diluent.

100%(700 PPM): Pipette out 5.0 from stock solution and dilute up to 10 ml with diluent.

120% (840 PPM): Pipette out 6.0 from stock solution and dilute up to 10 ml with diluent.

150%(1050 PPM): Pipette out 7.5 from stock solution and dilute up to 10 ml with diluent.

Figure 20.0 Overlay Chromatogram of five different concentrations of Esmolol Hydrochloride

Sr. No.	Linearity level	Concentration (PPM)	Area 1	Area 2	Area %RSD
1	50%	350	2395.89	2396.45	0.02
2	80%	560	3738.75	3726.77	0.23
3	100%	700	4750.36	4753.69	0.05
4	120%	840	5695.20	5687.27	0.10
5	150%	1050	7069.67	7069.81	0.00
Correlation coefficient obtained			0.9997	0.9996	-
y-intercept			26.215	22.005	-
Slope			6.7197	6.7211	-
Average Correlation coefficient obtained			0.99965		-
y-intercept Standard Deviation			2.977		-
Average Slope			6.7204		-

Table 6.0 Calibration data for Esmolol Hydrochloride (n=5)

Figure 21.0: Calibration curve of Esmolol Hydrochloride

DISCUSSION

Linearity range for Esmolol Hydrochloride and Misoprostol was found to be in the range of 350 to 1050 µg/ml.

Range:

Range is the interval between upper and lower concentration of analyte in sample for which it has been demonstrated that the analytical method has suitable level of precision, accuracy and linearity. The linear response was observed over range of 350-1050 µg/ml for Esmolol Hydrochloride.

PPM	350 µg/ml	1050 µg/ml
Area 1	2395.89	7069.67
Area 2	2396.45	7069.81
Avg	2396.17	7069.74
SD	0.28	0.07
%RSD	0.01	0.00

Table 7.0 Range Data

Precision

Precision of analytical procedure express the closeness of agreement between the value, which is accepted either as a conventional true value or as an accepted reference value and the value found.

Injection -4	4593.44
Injection -5	4588.06
AVG.	4592.15
SD	2.31
%RSD	0.05%

Table 8.0 Area of 5 replicate standard injections

System Precision/Repeatability

Prepared standard solution as per method.

Sr. No.	Area
Injection -1	4593.43
Injection -2	4593.12
Injection -3	4592.68

Method Precision/Intermediate precision Day 1

Repeatability of the method for the estimation of assay for Esmolol hydrochloride Repeatability expresses the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time.

Blank, standard solution and sample solution prepared as per method.

Injections	Standard solution	Sample solution
	Area	Area
Injection-1	4593.43	4516.9
Injection-2	4593.12	4513.75
Injection-3	4592.68	4520.53
injection-4	4593.44	4521.59
Injection-5	4588.06	4523.1
Injection-6	-	4523.23
AVG	4592.15	4519.85
SD	2.31	3.78
%RSD	0.05	0.08

Table 9.0 Observation of method precision

Discussion and Conclusion: %RSD of five replicate standard injections is within acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%) and %RSD of test solution is within acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%)

Intermediate Method Precision (Day 2)

For day 2- same instrument, different day and different analyst

Injections	Standard solution	Sample solution
	Area	Area
Injection-1	4581.5	4508.98
Injection-2	4572.99	4505.78
Injection-3	4574.74	4505.68
injection-4	4571.78	4506.39
Injection-5	4571.32	4510.5
Injection-6	-	4508.28
AVG	4574.47	4507.6
SD	4.15	1.96
%RSD	0.09%	0.04%

Table 10.0 Observation for Day 2 precision results

Mean of Day 1 and Day 2 precision

Injections		Standard solution	Sample solution
		Area	Area
Day 1 / Method precision	Injection-1	4593.43	4516.9
	Injection-2	4593.12	4513.75
	Injection-3	4592.68	4520.53
	injection-4	4593.44	4521.59
	Injection-5	4588.06	4523.1
	Injection-6	-	4523.23
Day 2	Injection-1	4581.5	4508.98
	Injection-2	4572.99	4505.78
	Injection-3	4574.74	4505.68
	injection-4	4571.78	4506.39
	Injection-5	4571.32	4510.5
	Injection-6	-	4508.28
Average		4583.31	4513.73
SD		9.34	6.71
%RSD		0.20	0.15

Table 11.0 Observation mean results of Day 1 and Day 2

Discussion and Conclusion: % RSD between day 2 with Method precision or day 1 standard solution area is within acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%) % RSD between day 2 and Method precision or day 1 test solution area is within acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%).

Accuracy

Accuracy of an analytical procedure express the closeness to the agreement between the value,

which is accept either as a conventional true value and the test result.

Demonstrate the accuracy of the test method by preparing recovery samples at the level 80%,100% and 120% if target concentration. Prepare the recovery samples in triplicate at each level and as per sample solution.

$$\% \text{ Recovery} = (\text{Experimental value}/\text{Actual value}) \times 100$$

Level	Amount spiked in solution (ppm)	Area	Amount added (ppm)	Amount recovered (ppm)	%Recovery
80%	560	3732.56	561.0	550.8	98.35%
80%	560	3743.53			
80%	560	3699.34			
100%	700	4752.94	701.0	701.6	100.23%
100%	700	4740.00			
100%	700	4743.67			
120%	840	5683.29	841.0	838.8	99.86%
120%	840	5662.31			

120%	840	5675.15		
Avg.				99.48%
SD				1.00
%RSD				1.00%

Table 12.0 % Recovery result

Discussion: Result obtain reveals that % recovery was Esmolol Hydrochloride by this method was found within the range of acceptance criteria in ICH i.e 98.35 – 99.86%

$$= 10 * 2.977 / 6.7204$$

$$= 4.430 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

LOD and LOQ:

Calibration curve was repeated for five times and the standard deviation of the intercept was calculated. Then LOD and LOQ were calculated as follows.

Limit of Detection:

$$\text{LOD} = \frac{3.3\sigma}{S}$$

$$= 3.3 * 2.977 / 6.7204$$

$$= 1.462 \mu\text{g/ml}$$

Limit of Quantification:

$$\text{LOQ} = \frac{10\sigma}{S}$$

Discussion:

The propose method can detect Esmolol Hydrochloride at low level and it also quantified small amount of drug precisely. So, it was concluded that the proposed method is very sensitive in nature.

Robustness

Variation in Flow rate : Variated flow rate ± 0.1 ml/min. (1.4 ml/min and 1.6 ml/min)

Mobile phase, blank, standard solution and Sample solution prepared as per method.

Injection	Area of Esmolol hydrochloride	
	1.4 ml/min	1.6 ml/min
Standard 1	5219.42	4261.77
Standard 2	5226.70	4262.46
Standard 3	5227.83	4260.35
Standard 4	5229.78	4262.21
Standard 5	5232.19	4262.62
Sample 1	5182.55	4220.26
Sample 2	5179.43	4233.35
% Assay	100.41%	100.47%
% Assay Average	100.44%	
% Assay SD	0.04	
% Assay RSD	0.04%	

Table 13.0 Robustness result for Flow rate

Conclusion:

% RSD of Assay Esmolol hydrochloride is within acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%)

Variation in Wavelength: Variated in wavelength ± 1 nm (220 nm and 222 nm)

Mobile phase, blank, standard solution and Sample solution prepared as per method.

Injection	Area of Esmolol hydrochloride	
	220 nm	222 nm
Standard 1	5088.81	4271.38
Standard 2	5089.09	4277.34
Standard 3	5089.06	4272.13
Standard 4	5088.88	4275.33
Standard 5	5083.76	4276.37
Sample 1	5034.97	4231.32
Sample 2	5011.01	4210.70
% Assay	100.01%	100.04%
% Assay Average	100.03%	
% Assay SD	0.02	
% Assay RSD	0.02%	

Table 14.0 Robustness result for wavelength

Conclusion:

Stability of solution (Standard solution)

% RSD of Assay of Esmolol hydrochloride is within acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%)

Mobile phase, blank, standard solution and Sample solution prepared as per method.

Sr. No.	Time (Hr.)	Area	% Difference in area
1.	0	4690.93	0.00%
2.	2	4674.88	0.34%
3.	4	4665.55	0.54%
4.	6	4659.54	0.67%
5.	8	4659.42	0.67%
6.	10	4650.33	0.87%
7.	12	4643.12	1.02%

Conclusion: % Difference between the initial area and respective time interval value is within Acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%)

Stability of test solution

Sr. No.	Time (Hr.)	Std area	Test Area	Assay	% Difference in Assay
1.	0	4690.93	4539.75	98.93%	0.00%
2.	2	4674.88	4533.32	99.12%	-0.20%
3.	4	4665.55	4525.04	99.14%	-0.22%
4.	6	4659.54	4527.27	99.32%	-0.39%
5.	8	4659.42	4514.76	99.05%	-0.12%
6.	10	4650.33	4511.07	99.16%	-0.23%
7.	12	4643.12	4508.73	99.26%	-0.34%

Conclusion: % Difference between the initial % assay and respective time interval value is within Acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%)

These %RSD value was found to be less than ± 2.0 indicated that the method is precise. No significant changes in the Peak area were observed, proving that the developed method is rugged and robust.

Chromatogram of the Test solution containing 700 μ g/ml of Esmolol Hydrochloride was recorded and peak areas were noted for estimation of Esmolol Hydrochloride. The concentration of Esmolol Hydrochloride in formulation was determined against the standard Esmolol Hydrochloride.

Application of the proposed method for analysis of Esmolol Hydrochloride in formulation.

Figure 22.0 Chromatogram of Esmolol Hydrochloride

SUMMARY OF VALIDATION PARAMETER ON HPLC

Summary of validation parameter are shown in below table. All the parameters for substance met the criteria of ICH guideline for the method validation and found to be suitable for routine quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The result of linearity, accuracy, precision

proved to be within limits with lower limits of detection and quantification. Robustness of method was confirmed as no significant in the were observed on analysis by subjecting the method to slight change in the method condition. Assay results obtained by proposed method are fair agreement.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Acceptance Criteria	Results
			Esmolol hydrochloride
1.	System suitability	The % RSD for area of five replicate of standard solutions should not be more than 2.0%	0.15%
2.	Specificity	There should be no interference absorbance of Placebo solution, diluting solution as blank, standard solution.	There is no interference absorbance of Placebo solution, diluting solution as blank, standard solution.
3.	Precision		
3.1.	System Precision	NMT 2.0% (% of Relative standard deviation)	0.05%

Sr. No.	Parameter	Acceptance Criteria	Results
			Esmolol hydrochloride
3.2.	Method Precision	NMT 2.0% (% of Relative standard deviation)	0.08%
3.3.	Intermediate Precision	NMT 2.0% (% of Relative standard deviation)	0.16%
4.	Linearity	The co-relation co-efficient should be not less than 0.99.	0.99965
5.	Range	NMT 2% (% of Relative Standard Deviation)	% of Relative Standard Deviation = NMT 2%
6.	Accuracy/Recovery	NMT 2.0% (% of Relative standard deviation)	% of Relative Standard Deviation = NMT 2%
7.	Stability of Analytical solution	% Difference between the initial % assay and respective time interval value is within Acceptance criteria (NMT 2.0%)	Standard Solution and Sample Solution is stable upto 12 hours. % of Relative Standard Deviation = NMT 2%
8.	Robustness		
8.1.	Flow Rate	NMT 2.0%	0.04%
8.2.	Wavelength	(% of Relative standard deviation)	0.02%
9.	LOD	NA	1.462 µg/ml
10.	LOQ	NA	4.430 µg/ml

CONCLUSION

A simple, economic, specific, accurate and precise Stability indicating RP- HPLC methods have been developed and validated for the estimation of Esmolol Hydrochloride in semi solid dosage form. All method validation parameters lie within its acceptance criteria as per ICH Q2(R1) guideline so we can conclude that methods are specific, linear, accurate and precise.

In RP-HPLC method, Linearity was observed in the concentration rang 350-1050µg/ml with correlation coefficient of Esmolol Hydrochloride (R²) 0.999. The proposed method was successfully applied for the simultaneous estimation of both drugs in combined dosage form. The assay value of Esmolol Hydrochloride was found to be 100.61%. The Mean recovery were found to be in the range 98.35 – 99.86%. LOD and LOQ were found to be 1.462 µg/ml and 4.430 µg/ml for Esmolol Hydrochloride. The % RSD of repeatability precision, method precision, and

intraday precision of Esmolol Hydrochloride was found to be 0.05%, 0.08% and 0.16%. it indicated that the method is precise. The % RSD of Robustness change in wavelength Esmolol Hydrochloride was found to be 0.02%. The % RSD of Robustness change in Flow rate Esmolol Hydrochloride was found to be 0.04%. Hence, proposed method is well suited for assay of Esmolol Hydrochloride in its semi solid dosage form. it can be easily and conveniently adopted for routine analysis of semi solid dosage form.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Authors have no conflict of interest.

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